

Source: [Heravi, M.M.](#), Zadsirjan, V., Shiri, M., Hosseinnejad, T., Shintre, S. A., Koorbanally, N. A. (2017), Molecular diversity in cyclization of Ugi-products leading to the synthesis of 2,5-diketopiperazines: computational study, Journal of Research on Chemical Intermediates, 43(4), [doi: 10.1007/s11164-016-2750-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11164-016-2750-1)

Molecular diversity in cyclization of Ugi-products leading to the synthesis of 2,5-diketopiperazines: computational study

[Majid M. Heravi](#)¹, Vahideh Zadsirjan, Morteza Shiri, Tayebeh Hosseinnejad, Suhas A. Shintre, Neil A. Koorbanally

¹ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics & Chemistry Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

Ugi-adducts were obtained via a one-pot four-component reaction of divergent aldehydes, amines, aroylacrylic acids and isocyanide in methanol. These products were subjected to intramolecular Michael addition in the presence of K₂CO₃ in DMF at room temperature to afford a single product. Literally, the formation of two heterocyclic systems, 6-membered diones or 7-membered diones are possible, which could not be identified by conventional spectroscopic methods. The X-ray crystallographical data was obtained for one selected product, which indicated preferential formation of the corresponding 6-membered dione. In order to establish the generality of this mode of cyclization, the quantum chemistry calculations were performed. The obtained results confirmed the favorable formation of 6-membered diones in the gas and also several solution phases. All the products were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Keywords

2,5-Diketopiperazines, Aroylacrylic acids, Base catalysis, Density functional theory, Intramolecular Michael addition, Molecular diversity, Polarized continuum model, Ugi reaction, Addition reactions, Computation theory, Continuum mechanics, Quantum chemistry, Quantum theory, Spectroscopic analysis, 2,5-diketopiperazines, Antibacterial and antifungal activity, Polarized continuum models, Cyclization.